

Original article

Mucocutaneous manifestations in human immunodeficiency virus-infected children seen at a treatment centre in northwestern Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background: Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection is conceivably the greatest pandemic that humanity has faced in the last four decades. Mucocutaneous manifestations constitute one of the most common clinical features in children. Commonly, mucocutaneous lesions are the initial presenting symptoms and could also be a pointer to the deteriorating immune function of such patients. **Objectives:** This study was conducted to determine the pattern and prevalence of mucocutaneous manifestations in HIV-infected children accessing care in a tertiary healthcare centre in Northwestern Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** Three hundred and eighty-three children who were HIV infected, aged six months to 15 years, were evaluated over eight months for mucocutaneous lesions. Patients were categorised into three age groups: less than six years, six to 12 years, and greater than 12 years. The spectrum of mucocutaneous disorders were itemized as infectious/infestation, pigmentary, inflammatory, nail abnormality, and miscellaneous. **Results:** Three hundred and eighty-three HIV-infected children were consecutively recruited into the study; 209 (54.6%) were males, and 174 (45.4%) were females. Three hundred and seventy-three (97.4%) participants were on ART. The prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders was 172 (44.9%), and the most prevalent mucocutaneous disorder was infestation/infectious dermatosis 98 (41.7%), followed by pigmentary lesions 65 (27.7%). A high preponderance of mucocutaneous disorders was observed among males, 99 (47.4%), compared to females. However, there was no statistically significant association between the prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders and gender, $P=0.289$. Also, children between six and 12 years had the highest lesions, 95 (46.6%). The association between age group and mucocutaneous disorders was not statistically significant ($P=0.781$). **Conclusions:** Mucocutaneous disorders in pediatric HIV/AIDS are common and may have atypical presentations, most of which have infectious aetiology. The manifestation may vary in different parts of the world. In Africa, disorders of infectious origin predominate, while in the Indian subcontinent, purpuric pruritic eruption is more common. HIV-infected children with immunosuppression do present with multiple mucocutaneous diseases.

Keywords: Human immunodeficiency virus, Infestation, Manifestation, Mucocutaneous, Nigeria.

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Introduction

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is the aetiological agent of acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS).¹ The disease was first described in 1981, and HIV-1 was isolated by 1983. Since the description, AIDS has become a worldwide pandemic, expanding in scope and magnitude.² The infection causes a profound immunodeficiency resulting primarily from a progressive qualitative and quantitative deficiency of the subset of T lymphocytes referred to as helper T cells.¹ This results in a greater susceptibility to infectious, noninfectious inflammatory, and malignant conditions that affect virtually every organ in the body, including the skin. The skin is the largest

organ in the body.³ It has multiple functions, including temperature regulation, fluid balance, sensation, immunological protection from ultraviolet light damage, and expression of racial characteristics. Cutaneous and mucosal complications eventually occur in nearly all individuals with HIV infection. Ninety percent of patients with HIV have dermatological manifestations at some stage during their disease.^{4,5}, which can be debilitating, disfiguring, and life-threatening.

The spectrum of skin disorders depends on the immunological stage as reflected by CD4 cell count/percent, concurrent use of ART, and pattern of endemic infections.⁶ The incidence, severity, and number of skin lesions increase as immune function deteriorates.⁵ There is a correlation between the increasing number and severity of mucocutaneous lesions and declining immunity mirrored by CD4 cell count.⁵ After the introduction of antiretroviral therapy (ART), there has been a decrease in the incidence and severity of HIV-associated mucocutaneous lesions commonly seen in the pre-ART era.⁷ The prevalence of mucocutaneous manifestations in HIV-infected children from various parts of the world ranges from 42% to 93%.⁸ Two studies done in Thailand at two different times found a prevalence of 51.6%⁹ and 52%¹⁰, respectively. However, higher rates were found in India 89.4%,¹¹ Ethiopia (72.6%),¹² Tanzania 85%¹³ and Chile 56%,¹⁴ respectively. In West Africa, a study done in Guinea Conakry showed a prevalence of 54.6%.¹⁵ A prevalence of 61% was also reported from the Republic of Benin.¹⁶ In Nigeria, studies done in Benin showed 64%¹⁷ while that of Ibadan was 53.5%¹⁸ and Gwagwalada 52.2%.¹⁹ Several studies reported mucocutaneous disorders as more common in those with advanced HIV disease using either the WHO clinical staging or immunological classification.^{9,10,12,13,17-19} Infective skin diseases were usually the most common, especially fungal skin infections.^{14,13,20} Common HIV-associated dermatoses, such as candidiasis, dermatophyte infections, and herpes simplex virus infections, have all diminished since the introduction of ART.²¹⁻²³

Materials and Methods

Study design: The study was a descriptive, cross-sectional, hospital-based study.

Study Population: All HIV-infected children under the age of 15 years who were diagnosed (by a positive DNA PCR in those six months to 18 months, as is the gold standard for early infant HIV diagnosis because it avoids false positives from

maternal antibodies and enables immediate ART initiation, and a positive ELISA test in those more than 18 months of age to 15 years) attending the HIV care and treatment centre at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Shika-Zaira.

Inclusion Criteria: All children between six months and 15 years old with confirmed HIV infection, including newly diagnosed cases and those already on care and treatment, whose parents or guardians gave consent.

Exclusion Criteria: Children whose parents/caregivers did not consent and those on hydroxyurea, ketoconazole, or iron supplements.

Data collection: Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV)-positive children between six months and fifteen years attending the HIV Care and Treatment Centre ABUTH were recruited over eight months from January to August 2019. Children who met the inclusion criteria were consecutively recruited until the desired sample size was attained. Socio-demographic information, including age, gender, social class, and clinical history, were obtained. A complete physical examination in a well-lit room after proper exposure of each child was carried out to identify all possible mucocutaneous disorders. Most lesions were diagnosed clinically, relevant investigations were done whenever indicated, skin scrapings were taken, and specimens were examined microscopically for fungal hyphae and spores. Swabs were also taken and sent for investigations as appropriate for confirmation of diagnosis, such as Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) examination, smears, cultures, biopsies, and serology. **Ethical Consideration:** Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health, Research, and Ethics Committee of ABUTH (ABUTH/HREC/A11/2017). Informed consent was obtained from the respective caregiver of the child as applicable after a clear explanation of the study. Assent was also obtained from children aged seven years and above.

Data Analysis

Data was manually entered into a computer database and analysed using IBM's Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) program version 20. Measures of central tendency and spread were used to describe quantitative variables, while qualitative variables were presented in tables and charts. The chi-square test was used to determine any association, and the one-proportion binomial and chi-square goodness-of-fit tests of multiple proportions were used to test for any proportional differences. At the same time, binary

logistic regression was used to determine the relationship. A confidence interval of 95% and a p-value of ≤ 0.05 were considered significant.

Results

The total number of HIV-infected children recruited during this study was 383. There were 209 males (54.6%) and 174 females (45.4%), giving a ratio of 1.2:1. The age ranged from six months to 15 years, with a mean of 10.9 ± 3.4 years. Most (204) were between six and 12 years, constituting 53.3%. (Table 1)

Age Group (years)	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
<6	18(4.7)	14(3.6)	32(8.3)
6-12	114(29.8)	90(23.5)	204(53.3)
>12	77(20.1)	70(18.3)	147(38.4)
Total	209(55.6)	174(45.4)	383(100)

Of the HIV-infected children studied, 172 (44.9%) were found to have mucocutaneous.

Disorders with some having more than one lesion (Figures 1A & B, 2A & B). A proportion-binomial test was used to determine whether the proportion of those with mucocutaneous conditions was the same as those that do not have mucocutaneous disorders. The test statistics showed that the difference in proportions was statistically significant ($p = 0.046$). Table 2

Table 2: Prevalence of mucocutaneous diseases in the study population

Mucocutaneous lesions	Frequency	Percent	P-value ^a
Present	172	44.9	0.046
Absent	211	55.1	
Total	383	100	

^aTest proportion (binomial)

Fig 1A: Epidermodysplasia Verruciformis

Fig 1B: Herpes Zoster

Fig 2A: Tinea Capitis with Scarring

Fig 2B. Tinea Corporis

A high preponderance of mucocutaneous disorders was observed among males, 99 (47.4%), compared to females. However, there was no statistically significant association between the prevalence of mucocutaneous diseases and gender ($\chi^2=1.125$, df 1, $p=0.289$). Also, children between six and 12 years had the highest lesions, 95 (46.6%). The association between age group and mucocutaneous disorders was also not statistically significant ($\chi^2=0.495$, df 2, $p=0.781$). Table 3

Table 3: Age and Sex Distribution of Mucocutaneous Disorders in the Study Population

Mucocutaneous Lesions					
	Absent (%)	Present (%)	Total (%)	Chisqr(df)	P
Gender					
Male	110 (52.6)	99(47.4)	209 (100)	1.125 (1)	0.289
Female	101 (58.0)	73 (42.0)	174 (100)		
Total	211 (55.1)	172 (44.9)	383 (100)		
Age (years)					
<6	18 (56.3)	14 (43.8)	32 (100)	0.495 (2)	0.781
6-12	109 (53.4)	95 (46.6)	204 (100)		
>12	84 (57.1)	63 (42.9)	63 (42.9)		

Different types of mucocutaneous disorders were seen among the participants, with 235 lesions seen during the study. These varied from infectious (Figure 3A) to noninfectious (Figure 3B). The infectious/infestation disorders were the highest at 98 (41.7%), followed by pigmentary disorders at 65 (27.7%). Malignant conditions were not seen.

Fig. 3A Tinea Capitis

Fig 3B: Vitisigo

There was a statistically significant difference in the proportions amongst the study population between those with infectious/infestation, inflammatory,

pigmentary, nail abnormality, and miscellaneous lesions.

($\chi^2 = 107.319$, df 4, $p < 0.0001$). Table 4

Table 4: Distribution showing the pattern of mucocutaneous disorders in the study population.

Spectrum of Mucocutaneous Disorders	Frequency	Percent
Infectious/Infestation	98	41.7
Pigmentary	65	27.7
Inflammatory	41	17.4
Nail abnormality	24	10.2
Miscellaneous	7	3
Total	235	100

Chi-sqr(pdf) = 107.32(4) P-value = 0.0001
 Test of Multiple Proportions = < 0.0001
 Miscellaneous: Cancrum oris, angular cheilitis, and brownish silky hair.

Table 5 shows the distribution of mucocutaneous disorders related to ART regimen and duration. Among the subjects on the first line, 144 (41.7%) had lesions, while 22 (78.6%) of those on the second line had lesions. The association between the prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders and ART regimen was statistically significant ($\chi^2=14.255$, df 1, $p < 0.0001$). For ART duration, 134 (43.5%) of those who had been on ART for more than 18 months had lesions, while 32 (49.2%) of those who were on ART for less than 18 months had lesions. There was no statistically significant association between the prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders and ART duration ($\chi^2=0.712$, df 1, $p=0.399$). Table 5

Table 5: Regimen and duration of ART and the occurrence of mucocutaneous disorders among 373 HIV-infected subjects

	Mucocutaneous Lesions			Chisqr (df)	P-value
	Absent (%)	Present (%)	Total (%)		
ART Regimen					
1 st Line	201 (53.8)	144(41.7)	345 (100)	14.26 (1)	<0.0001
2 nd Line	6 (14.0)	22 (78.6)	28 (100)		
Total	207 (55.5)	166 (44.5)	373 (100)		
Duration on ART (months)					
<18	33 (50.8)	32 (49.2)	65 (100)	0.712(1)	0.399
>18	174 (56.5)	134 (43.5)	308 (100)		
Total	84 (57.1)	63 (42.9)	147 (100)		

Discussion:

The prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders in this study was 44.9%. This falls within the global range of 42% to 93%,⁸ but at the lower range. There was significant association between the prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders and ART despite early commencement of treatment as recommended in the new national guideline that ART be initiated in all HIV-infected children regardless of the WHO clinical stage, CD4 cell count, or percentage.²⁴ This restores and prevents deterioration of the immune function. This assertion is supported by the high percentage (97.4%) of children with HIV already on therapy in this study. In addition, the majority, 82.6%, have been on ART for more than 18 months, which is considered the average time expected to restore the immune function, where most clinical and immunological derangement reverses after successful treatment with ART.²⁵ The mean duration of treatment with ART in this study was 6.6 ± 3.5 years. The findings in this study contrast with other studies that reported very high prevalence rates of mucocutaneous disorders by Kondreddy *et al.*,¹¹ in India (89.4%), Panya *et al.*,¹³ in Tanzania 85%, Endayehu *et al.*,¹² in Ethiopia (72.6%), and Umoru *et al.*,¹⁷ in Benin, Nigeria (60%). Other studies also reported prevalence rates between 51.6% and 56%.^{9,14,15,18,19} These studies were done more than seven years ago (most more than ten years ago) when the policy to treat all HIV-infected children was not in place, and the criteria for the initiation of ART were based on WHO clinical and immunological staging, therefore excluding some patients from benefiting from treatment. That was why the percentage of patients on ART from those studies was relatively lower, between 55.8% and 75.4%, and most of them were on ART for less than 18 months,^{11,12,13} which might not have been long enough for immune restoration. ART suppresses HIV viral replication, preventing disease progression, allowing the reconstitution and restoration of the immune function, reducing opportunistic infections, and significantly improving clinical outcomes.²⁶ This ultimately improves the quality of life of HIV-infected children. Furthermore, the low prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders in this study could be a result of improved access to comprehensive HIV care, which includes access to ongoing counselling, baseline and routine laboratory investigations, prevention and treatment of opportunistic infections, monitoring, and follow-up.²⁴

Infections and infestations were the most common mucocutaneous disorders seen in this study. This report is inconsistent with the findings in the works of Wananukul *et al.*,¹⁰ Wananukul and Thisyakom,⁹ Lim *et al.*,²⁷ and Stefanaki *et al.*²⁸

This study did not demonstrate any significant association between age and gender with mucocutaneous disorders. These findings were like those by Endayehu *et al.*,¹² Panya *et al.*,¹³ and Umoru *et al.*,¹⁷ where differences in age and gender were not significantly associated with the prevalence of mucocutaneous disorders. This is because mucocutaneous disorders are more greatly influenced by immune status, as the primary effect of HIV is on the immune system, where there is CD4 cell dysfunction and depletion.²⁶ The pattern of mucocutaneous disorders in this study included infestation/infectious, pigmentary, inflammatory, and nail abnormalities. Malignant disorders were, however, not seen throughout the study. Infestation/infectious dermatosis was the most frequent, seen in 98 (41.7%) participants. In similar studies, the higher prevalence of infectious dermatosis could result from the impairment of the skin's immune system early in the natural history of HIV infection. This is due to the specific loss of antigen-presenting dendritic cells, which HIV directly infects, and a shift from the normal T-helper 1-dominated immune response characterized by promoting cell-mediated immunity to a T-helper 2-dominated immune response.²⁹ Furthermore, infectious dermatosis pre-dominance in this cohort could reflect the pattern of endemic infections in the environments where the studies were conducted. Transmissible diseases, both infectious and infestations, make up most of the skin diseases in sub-Saharan Africa.³⁰ A high percentage of 78.6% of HIV-infected children on second-line ART regimens were observed to have mucocutaneous disorders compared to 41.7% of those on first-line ART. This could mean they have not adequately restored and reconstructed their immune function or, probably, an adverse drug reaction. Failure to restore and reconstitute the immune function might result from treatment failure of the second-line ART regimen. This could be because the reasons for their initial treatment failure might not have been adequately addressed, e.g., suboptimal adherence, malnutrition, etc. Second-line ART treatment failure was high among HIV-infected patients, including children in sub-Saharan Africa, especially within 12-18 months of commencement of therapy.³¹ High baseline viral load, lower peak values for CD4 cells,

and advanced WHO clinical stage at baseline, weight, and use of traditional medications were factors linked with the occurrence of second-line treatment failure.³¹

In this research, only a one-time examination was conducted. HIV-infected children may have more and different infections and infestations, especially when their disease progresses with treatment failure.

Conclusions

Mucocutaneous disorders in pediatric HIV/AIDS commonly occur and may have atypical presentations, most of which have infectious aetiology, as demonstrated in this study. The manifestation may vary in different parts of the globe. In Africa, disorders of infectious origin predominate, while in the Indian subcontinent, purpuric pruritic eruption was the commonest condition. HIV-infected children with immunosuppression may present with multiple mucocutaneous manifestations at the same time. There is a need for further studies to assess the relationship between access to care and support services of HIV-infected children and mucocutaneous disorders.

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